

RELATIONSHIP OF C-REACTIVE PROTEIN WITH DIET, PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AND ANTHROPOMETRIC MEASUREMENT IN SCHOOL GOING FEMALE CHILDREN

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DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20021899>

Keywords

Article History

Received: 26 January 2026

Accepted: 11 March 2026

Published: 25 March 2026

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Abstract

Background Creactive protein (CRP) is a biomarker of systemic inflammation that has been linked to obesity, dietary patterns, and cardiometabolic risk. Children are particularly vulnerable to lifestyle-related changes in diet and physical activity, which may influence CRP levels and long-term health outcomes.

Objectives This study aimed to assess the relationship between plasma CRP levels, dietary intake, physical activity, and anthropometric measurements among school-going girls in District Swabi, Pakistan.

Methodology A cross-sectional study was conducted among 80 randomly selected healthy girls aged 12–17 years. Anthropometric measurements were recorded using standardized procedures. Dietary intake was assessed through 24-hour dietary recall and food frequency questionnaires. Physical activity was measured using the Physical Activity Questionnaire for Older Children (PAQ-C) and Adolescents (PAQ-A). After an overnight fast, venous blood samples were collected in EDTA tubes for CRP analysis. Statistical analyses included descriptive statistics, independent sample t-tests, Pearson correlation, and chi-square tests.

Results The mean age, weight, and BMI of participants were 14.53 ± 1.73 years, 46.51 ± 4.59 kg, and 22.48 ± 4.34 kg/m², respectively. Overall, 12.5% were obese, 15.0% overweight, and 61.3% within the normal BMI range. Girls categorized as “at risk” based on CRP levels had significantly higher mean weight (48.15 ± 4.29 kg), BMI (24.50 ± 4.67 kg/m²), waist circumference (81.51 ± 11.43 cm), and waist-to-hip ratio (0.89 ± 0.08) compared to the normal group ($p < 0.01$). Dietary analysis revealed higher caloric intake, fats, and cholesterol in the at-risk group, whereas fiber and vitamin A intake were significantly higher in the normal group ($p = 0.005$). Physical activity showed no significant association with CRP levels.

Conclusion Elevated CRP levels were directly associated with adiposity and dietary fat/cholesterol intake, while fiber and vitamin A intake demonstrated protective associations. These findings underscore the importance of early dietary and lifestyle interventions to reduce inflammation-related health risks in adolescent populations.

INTRODUCTION

C-reactive protein (CRP) is an acute-phase protein that serves as a key marker of inflammation and infection (Kushner, 2023). CRP is sometimes termed high-sensitivity or ultra-sensitive protein (Ridker, 2009). It was first discovered by William Tillet and Thomas Francis at Rockefeller University in 1930 (Ridker, 2009). Later, Oswald Avery and Maclyn McCarty observed elevated plasma CRP in patients with diverse inflammatory stimuli (Espe et al., 2007). CRP is primarily produced in the liver, with normal concentrations below 10 mg/L, but recent studies show production by non-hepatic cells such as lymphocytes, neurons, Kupffer cells, and monocytes (Sadeghi Pour et al., 2010). Concentrations vary by age (Ford et al., 2003), with reported averages of 4.1 mg/L in men, 5.5 mg/L in women, and 0.3 mg/L in children (Wong et al., 2001; Ford et al., 2005). CRP binds to phosphocholine on damaged cells and bacterial polysaccharides. In healthy individuals, its plasma half-life is ~19 hours (Vigushin et al., 1993). Levels rise rapidly during infection, sometimes increasing 1,000-fold, and decline upon recovery (Laaksonen et al., 2004; Haverkate et al., 1997).

CRP has been studied as a marker of systemic diseases, including cardiovascular disease (Visser et al., 2000). Concentrations as low as 2.22–4.99 mg/L have been linked to heart disease in adults (Wong et al., 2001). Elevated CRP is associated with cardiovascular disease (Ridker et al., 1997), type II diabetes (Ford, 1999), metabolic syndrome (Laaksonen et al., 2004), increased BMI (Ortega et al., 2008; Siervo et al., 2012), and low cardiorespiratory fitness (Isasi et al., 2003). Childhood CRP levels also predict later disease risk (Berenson, 2002; Sun et al., 2008; Morrison et al., 2008). CRP is strongly associated with cardiovascular risk factors in children, including BMI, blood pressure, insulin resistance, LDL, and adipocytokines (Yoshida et al., 2006). Genetic studies suggest CRP has heritable components (Pankow et al., 2001), while obesity is a major predictor (Thomas et al., 2008). In adults, CRP correlates positively with age, obesity, smoking, lipid profile, and cardiovascular disease, and inversely with HDL cholesterol (Misera et al., 2002).

Diet plays a critical role in modulating CRP. Nutrition influences infection and inflammation (Grimble, 1999; Chung et al., 2001). Diets high in refined carbohydrates, saturated and trans fats, and low in vegetables and omega-3 fatty acids are linked to elevated CRP (Giugliano, 2006; Barbaresko et al., 2013). Conversely, fruit and vegetable intake reduce CRP (Ford et al., 2000). Adherence to the Mediterranean diet is associated with lower CRP concentrations (Estruch, 2010; Bedard et al., 2015).

Physical activity is another determinant of CRP. Active individuals have reduced cardiovascular risk (Cooper et al., 2005). Physical fitness is a strong health indicator (Metter et al., 2002), and studies show inverse associations between CRP and physical fitness in children (Isasi et al., 2003; Jarvisalo, 2002). Anyhow, this study was designed to investigate the relation of CRP with diet, physical activity, lifestyle, and anthropometric measures (weight, height, BMI, waist circumference, hip circumference, and waist-to-hip ratio) in school-going children of District Swabi.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study Location: The research study was carried out in district Swabi. Data was collected from both private and government school-going female children.

Study Design & sample selection: A Cross-sectional study was carried out in District Swabi. A sample of 80 girls was selected through randomized sampling method. Girls of age 12–17 years were enrolled in study free of disease. Those participants were enrolled in the study that were regular school-going and were free of any chronic disease. While those participants were excluded who had clinical record of chronic disease.

DATA COLLECTION: A well-constructed questionnaire was used for data collection regarding anthropometric measurement, socioeconomic status, demographic data and physical activity. To assess dietary and nutritional status, food frequency questionnaire and 24-hour dietary recall was used.

DEMOGRAPHIC AND SOCIOECONOMIC DATA: Socioeconomic and demographic data such as age, education level was collected from enrolled subjects using questionnaire.

ANTHROPOMETRIC MEASUREMENT: Anthropometric measurement was taken by assessing weight (kg), height (cm), body mass index (BMI), waist circumference (cm), hip circumference (cm), and waist-to-hip ratio (WHR) of the subject. World Health Organization procedures were followed for all measurements of the subjects (World Health Organization, 1995). Weight of the subject was measured through digital scale without heavy clothes and shoes and measured to the nearest 0.1 kg. Height was measured to the nearest 0.1 inch using stadiometer scale without shoes. The weight and height were used to find out the body mass index (BMI) using formula weight in kilogram divided by height in meter square. BMI of the subject was classified according to the Center for Disease Control and Prevention Growth Charts into underweight (<5th Percentile), normal (5th–85th Percentile), overweight (85th–95th Percentile) and obese (>95th Percentile) (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2000). Non-stretchable measuring tape was used to measure the waist circumference and reading was recorded to the nearest 0.5 cm. Waist-to-hip ratio (WHR) was measured by waist by the hip ratio.

PHYSICAL ACTIVITY: Physical activities of the children were measured by asking questions about routine daily activities. The physical activity questionnaire for older children (PAQ-C) and adolescents (PAQ-A) were used (Kowalski et al., 2004).

BIOCHEMICAL ASSESSMENT: Blood sample was taken from the children. 2 ml of the blood sample was collected in a disposable syringe. The blood samples from the syringe were transferred into EDTA tubes. The collected samples were then analyzed in laboratory to determine the C-reactive protein. C-reactive protein assay was carried out on CRP-turbidimetric kit. Children who had C-reactive protein level <1 mg/L were considered normal and those

having C-reactive protein level >3 mg/L were at risk (American Heart Association, 2003).

DIETARY ASSESSMENT: For dietary data, food frequency questionnaire and 24-hour dietary recall method was used. In 24-hour dietary recall method the children were asked about the food eaten during last 24 hours. Food frequency questionnaire was taken by recording all the commonly consumed food and drinks. To calculate energy, nutrient intake and amount of food eaten, relevant food composition tables for Pakistan were used.

DATA ANALYSIS: For data analysis SPSS (version 20) was used. Standard deviation, percentage, frequency and mean were determined. Independent sample t-test for continuous variables and for categorized variables chi-square test was performed to find out the comparison between normal and at-risk group with plasma C-reactive protein. Pearson correlation analysis was used to find out the relationship between C-reactive protein, diet, physical activity and anthropometric measurement. ANOVA was used to investigate the significance of the overall model of the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic and socioeconomic characteristics of the children

Results' regarding demographic and socioeconomic profiles of the children family is presented in Table 1. Mean age of the children was 14.53 ± 1.73 years. Among them 50% of the children were in the age of 12-14 years and remaining 50% were of age 15-17 years. 40% of the children were living in joint family system and 60.0% were in nuclear family. Family size and number of siblings of the children was 8.72 ± 3.84 and 4.81 ± 1.85 . 46.3% of the children's fathers were illiterate, 28.8% were matriculate, 16.3% had secondary and 8.8% had graduation. 48.8% of the children's fathers were jobless, 32.8% were labour or peon and 5.0% were lecturer or MD. 65.0% of the children mother were illiterate 13.8% were matriculate, 11.3% had secondary and only 10% had bachelor. 82.5% of the children's mothers were housewives while remaining were either teacher or health worker. Illiteracy and unemployment

ratio of the children’s parents were high in the present study. Socio economic conditions directly affect the availability of the food that was directly related to the nutritional status of the

children. Bradley et al. (2002) reported that low socioeconomic status affects health of the children that lead to morbidity and mortality.

Table 1: Demographic and socioeconomic characteristics of the children

Variables		Mean±SD / N (%)
Age of the subject(years)		14.53±1.73
Age of the subject Categories	12-14(years)	40
	15-17(years)	40
Family type	Joint	32(40.0%)
	Nuclear	48(60.0%)
Family size		8.72±3.84
Number of siblings		4.81±1.85
Father Education	Nil	37(46.3%)
	Matric	23(28.8%)
	Secondary	13(16.3%)
	Bachelor	7(8.8%)
Father Occupation	Jobless	39(48.8%)
	Laborer /Peon	26(32.8%)
	Office Assistant/ Shopkeeper	11(13.8%)
	Lecturer/MD	4(5.0%)
Mother Education	Nil	52(65.0%)
	Matric	11(13.8%)
	Secondary	9(11.3%)
	Bachelor	8(10.0%)
Mother Occupation	Housewife	66(82.5%)
	Teacher/ Health worker	14(17.5%)

SD=standard deviation, N= number, %= percentage

Anthropometric measurement of the children

Table 2 shows anthropometric measurement of the children. The mean weight of the children was 46.51±4.59kg. Mean height was 57.23±3.95inch and mean BMI of the children was 22.48±4.34kg/m². According to CDC classification 11.3% were below 5th-percentile (underweight). 61.3% were in range of 5th-85th percentile (normal), 15.0% were 85th-95th percentile (overweight) and 12.5% were >95th-percentile obese. Mean waist circumference of the subject was 76.77±11.29cm, hip

circumference was 88.53±9.55cm and WHR of the subject was 0.87±.06cm.

Our findings are in fair related to those of Khan et al. (2016). Who conducted a study on primary school going children in Karachi and observed that 34.9% of children were underweight (<5th-percentile), 63.44% normal (5th-95th percentile) and only 0.8% were overweight (>95th-percentile). The present study demonstrated that subject with high level of BMI, waist circumference had higher C-reactive protein

level. In adults' high level of C-reactive protein is an independent source of cardiovascular risk factors in later life.

Table 2. Anthropometric measurement of the children

Variables		Frequency (%), Mean±SD
Weight(kg)		46.51±4.59
Height(inch)		57.23±3.95
BMI (kg/m ²)		22.48±4.34
BMI percentile	Underweight <5 th -percentile	9(11.3%)
	Normal 5 th -85 th percentile	49(61.3%)
	Overweight 85 th -95 th percentile	12(15.0%)
	Obese >95 th -percentile	10(12.5%)
Waist circumference(cm)		76.77±11.29
Hip circumference(cm)		88.53±9.55
WHR (cm)		0.87±.06

BMI=body mass index, MUAC= mid upper arm circumference, WHR=waist to hip ratio

Physical activity of the children

Table 3 shows the physical activity of the children. Approximately 51.3% of the children had no physical activity while 48.8% had physical activity. 18.8% of the children do exercise daily, 12.5% 2-3days/week and 17.5% weekly. 31.3% of the subject had ½ hour physical activity and 17.5% had 1hour physical activity.32.5% of the children have moderate physical activity level and 16.2% were active. 33.8% of the children sleep for 1hour in a day while 27.5% do not sleep during day.

Our results are in resemblance with the study observed by Umair et al. (2011) who carried out study on physical activity of school children of age 5-12years at Lahore. It was observed that

47% of the children participate in physical activity 2-3days of week, 20% 3-4days/week and only 33% Participate 5-7days of the week. 51% of the children do their physical activity for 1hour. They concluded that Physical activity more than 2days a week had significant effect on child health increased energy expenditure and lower risk of being overweight. Similarly, children who walked to school were significantly high active as compared to those who travel by car (Ashely et al. 2005). Physical activities improve metabolic risk profile without inducing adiposity. Physical activities improve glucose transport and insulin action and improve oxygen supply and blood flow (Ekelund et al. 2006).

Table 3. Physical Activity of the children

Variables		Frequency, %
Exercise/other activity	Yes	39 (48.8%)
	No	41(51.3%)
Exercise Frequency	No physical activity	41(51.3%)
	Daily	15(18.8%)
	2-3days	10(12.5%)
	Weekly	14(17.5%)

Exercise duration	No physical activity	41(51.3%)
	1/2hour	25(31.3%)
	1hour	14(17.5%)
Physical activity level	Sedentary	41(51.3%)
	Moderate	26(32.5%)
	Active	13(16.2%)
Sleeping hour in a day	0 hour	22(27.5)
	1 hour	27(33.8)
	2 hours	24(33.8)
	2.50 hour	4(5.0)

Biochemical data of the children

Table 4 shows the biochemical data of the children. Mean C-reactive protein observed was 1.74±.84 based on the criteria of American heart association. Among them 51.3% were normal and 48.8% were at risk. Many markers of inflammation exist but C - reactive protein concentrations are easily accurately and relatively inexpensively measured. C-reactive protein is produced in liver and its

concentration increased rapidly during inflammation (Ford et al. 2003). Finding of the current research are in resemblance with work of Ford et al. (2005) who observed that among US children mean plasma C-reactive protein was 1.6mg/l, geometric mean 0.5mg/l and median 0.4mg/l. In present study about half of the children (48.8%) had high level of CRP. C-reactive protein level increased with obesity (Hamid et al. 2010).

Table 4. Biochemical data of the children

Variables		N (%), Mean ± SD
Quantitative C-reactive protein (mg/l)		1.74±.84
Quantitative C-reactive protein	Normal (0-1mg/l)	41(51.3%)
	At risk (>1mg/l)	39(48.8%)

SD= standard deviation, %=percentage, mg=milligram, N= number

Energy and dietary nutrient intake of the children

Energy and dietary intake of the children was shown in table 5. Dietary intakes of the children were calculated by using nutrient intake calculator. Mean caloric intakes of the children were 1904.42±349.42 kcal/day mean carbohydrate intakes was 189.61±78.01 g/day and mean protein, fats, fiber, cholesterol, vitamin A was 55.04±13.94 g/day, 84.02±19.75 g/day, 8.03±1.65 g/day, 97.95±60.54 mg/day and 53.59±6.71µg RE/day.

Finding of the current study are in resemblance with study of Fernandez. (2006) who observed

that participants consume 40% of their calories form fats, 16% protein and 44% from carbohydrates. The average cholesterol intake was also high than recommended dietary intake and 29% of Spanish children did not consume vegetables.

Results of the present research are in similarity with the study of Aziz et al. (2014) who demonstrated that children consumed 60 to 74% of their calories from carbohydrate, 18% to 32% from fat and 10 % to 12% from protein. It was reported that carbohydrate intake was high and protein intake was low. Imbalance

carbohydrate fat and protein intake could be due to lack of parent’s knowledge about food groups.

Table 5. Energy and dietary nutrient intake of the children

Variables	Mean ± SD
Calories (kcal/day)	1904.42±349.42
Carbohydrates (g/day)	189.61±78.01
Fats (g/day)	84.02±19.75
Protein (g/day)	55.04±13.94
Fiber (g/day)	8.03±1.65
Cholesterol (mg/day)	97.95±60.54
Vitamin A (R.E)	53.59±6.71

Kcal= kilocalories, g= gram, mg= milligram, R. E= retinol equivalent

Comparison of demographic and socioeconomic characteristics of the children on the basis of quantitative C-reactive protein

The comparison of demographic and socioeconomic characteristics of the children in normal and at-risk group on the basis of quantitative C-reactive proteins was shown in table 6. The Mean age(years) of the participants in normal and at-risk group were 14.41±1.68 and 14.65±1.80, respectively 55.0% of the subjects were at risk in age group of 12-14 years while 45.0% were normal. Number of siblings was high in at risk group (4.94±2.02) as compared to normal (4.68±1.69). Parents

education shows significant relation with quantitative plasma C- reactive protein. A significant difference (p<0.05) was observed in the parent’s education of normal and at-risk group.

A socioeconomic characteristic is an important factor of adult health outcome. Socioeconomic status affects the health of the children (Richard et al. 2017). Lindsey et al. (2005) also reported that low socioeconomic status is associated with poor health. C-reactive protein level was high in those subjects who have low income and education.

Table 6. Comparison of demographic and socioeconomic characteristics of the children on the basis of quantitative C-reactive protein

Variables	Quantitative CRP (Mean ± SD / N (%))		p-value
	Normal (N=41)	At risk (N=39)	
Age of the subject (years)	14.41±1.68	14.65±1.80	0.526**
Age of the subject Categories	12-14(years)	18(45.0%)	0.263*
	15-17(years)	32(57.5%)	
Family type	Joint	16(50.0%)	0.855*
	Nuclear	25(52.1%)	

Family size		8.24±2.46	9.23±4.87	0.253**
Number of siblings		4.68±1.69	4.94±2.02	0.525**
Father Education	Nil	26(70.3%)	11(29.7%)	0.001*
	Matric	8(34.8%)	15(65.2%)	
	Secondary	2(15.4%)	11(84.6%)	
	Bachelor	5(71.4%)	2(28.6%)	
Father Occupation	Jobless	22(56.4%)	17(43.6%)	0.110*
	Laborer/Peon	11(42.3%)	15(57.7%)	
	Office Assistant/Shopkeeper	4(36.4%)	7(63.6%)	
	Lecturer/MD	4(100.0%)	0(0.0%)	
Mother Education	Nil	28(53.8%)	24(46.2%)	0.014*
	Matric	9(81.8%)	2(18.2%)	
	Secondary	1(11.1%)	8(88.9%)	
	Bachelor	3(37.5%)	5(62.5%)	
Mother Occupation	Housewife	36(54.5%)	30(45.5%)	0.200*
	Teacher/Health worker	5(35.7%)	9(64.3%)	

*= chi-square test, **= independent sample t-test

Comparison of anthropometric measurement on the basis of quantitative C-reactive protein

Comparison of anthropometric measurement of the children between normal and at-risk group on the basis of quantitative C-reactive protein was shown in table 7. In at risk group of the children weight (kg), body mass index (kg/m²), waist circumference (cm), hip circumference (cm) and waist to hip ratio (cm) were significantly (p<0.05) high compared to normal group. Increased in weight, body mass index and waist circumference of the subject plasma C-reactive protein level was also increased. (Joshua Reid Vick. 2013) Results of the current study shows resemblance with the work of Vikram et al. (2003) who

perceived that overweight subject (BMI >85th percentile) (p=0.04) and subject with high values of waist and hip circumference (0.004) had significantly higher C-reactive protein level (0.007) as compared to those participants with lower values of variables. Wu et al. (2003) reported that C-reactive protein level is positively related to body mass index, waist circumference, hip circumference and waist to hip ratio. They concluded that children with the highest values of C-reactive protein were heavier and had higher body mass index. Wu et al. (2006) also reported that the plasma high sensitive c-reactive protein level was significantly correlated with anthropometric measurement such as weight, BMI, WC among school children.

Table 7. Comparison of anthropometric measurement on the basis of quantitative C-reactive protein

Variables	QUANTITATIVE CRP (Mean ± SD/ N (%))		p-value
	Normal (41)	At risk (39)	
Weight(kg)	44.60±4.06	48.15±4.29	0.000**
Height(inch)	58.24±3.26	56.17±4.37	0.019**
BMI (kg/m ²)	20.55±2.96	24.50±4.67	0.000**

BMI percentile	Underweight <5 th -percentile	5(55.6%)	4(44.4%)	0.005*
	Normal 5 th -85 th percentile	30(61.2%)	19(38.8%)	
	Overweight 85 th -95 th percentile	4(33.3%)	8(66.7%)	
	Obese >95 th -percentile	2(20%)	8(80.0%)	
Waist circumference(cm)		72.27±9.20	81.51±11.43	0.003**
Hip circumference(cm)		85.06±8.76	92.19±9.07	0.000**
WHR (cm)		0.84±.04	0.89±.08	0.005**

*= chi-square test, **= independent sample t-test

Comparison of physical activity on the basis of quantitative C-reactive protein

On the basis of quantitative C-reactive protein the comparison of physical activity between normal and at-risk group was shown in table 8. 53.8% of the children do exercise/physical activity daily in at risk group while 46.2% in normal group. 46.7% of the participants do exercise daily in normal group as compare to at risk group 53.3%. 60.0% do physical activity 2-3days in a week in at risk group while only 40.0% in normal group. 78.6% do exercise for 1 hour in at risk group while 21.4% in normal group. 61.5% of the children were physically active in at risk group while only 38.5% in

normal group. The present study shows no positive or significant relation between C-reactive protein and physical activity in children. This is may be due to small sample size or the children are in growing stage and show non-significant relation.

Our results are in resemblance with the previous study observed by Sobrinho et al. (2015) who also reported non-significant relation between C-reactive protein and physical activity in children of age 12-18 years. It may be possible that when C-reactive concentration is normal, physical activity may have little effect.

Table 8. Comparison of physical activity on the basis of quantitative C-reactive protein

Variables		QUANTITATIVE CRP (Mean±SD/ N (%))		p-value
		Normal (41)	At risk (39)	
Exercise/other activity	Yes	18(46.2%)	21(53.8%)	0.374
	No	23(56.1%)	18(43.9%)	
Exercise Frequency	No physical activity	23(56.1%)	18(43.9%)	0.795
	Daily	7(46.7%)	8(53.3%)	
	2-3days	4(40.0%)	6(60.0%)	
	Weekly	7(50.0%)	7(50.0%)	
Exercise duration	No physical activity	23(56.1%)	18(43.9%)	0.047
	1/2hour	15(60.0%)	10(40.0%)	
	1hour	3(21.4%)	11(78.6%)	
Physical activity level	Sedentary	23(56.1%)	18(43.9%)	0.535
	Moderate	13(50.0%)	13(50.0%)	
	Active	5(38.5%)	8(61.5%)	

Sleeping hour in a day	0 hour	10(45.5%)	12(54.5%)	0.240
	1 hour	14(51.9%)	13(48.1%)	
	2 hours	13(48.1%)	14(51.9%)	
	2.50 hour	4(100.0%)	0(0.0%)	

Comparison of caloric and dietary intake on the basis of C-reactive protein

The comparison of dietary intake on the basis of C-reactive protein in normal and at-risk group of the participants was shown in table 9. Mean caloric, fats, consumption of the children was high in at risk group 2212.07 ± 169.95 , 99.44 ± 11.21 as compared to normal 1611.78 ± 183.39 , 69.36 ± 14.09 and were highly significant ($p < 0.05$) which show that with increasing caloric and fats consumption C-reactive protein level was also increases. As compared to Caloric and fats intake, fiber and vitamin A intake was low in at risk group 7.47 ± 1.53 , 52.00 ± 6.39 as compared to normal group 8.57 ± 1.60 , 55.11 ± 6.74 and was in significant relation.

Our results show resemblance with observation of Aeberli et al. (2006). They suggested that high intake of saturated fatty acids inhibit low grade inflammation. Wu et al. (2001) also observed that high cholesterol, triglyceride increased the

C-reactive protein level and associated with cardiovascular disease in later life. Significant relation was found between high fiber intakes in girls of age 6-8 years with low level of C-reactive protein. Navarro et al. (2016) also reported that diet high in fruits and fiber vegetables have low C-reactive protein. Several studies have examined potential influence of fiber on plasma C-reactive protein level in adults. Supporting the fact that antioxidant nutrient may be responsible for lowering C-reactive protein level.

Ford et al. (2005) also reported that diet high in grain consumption was inversely related to elevated C-reactive protein level compared with the participants who have low level of grain consumption. Research has shown that nutrients can affect inflammation. It was reported that girls with poor quality diet show high level of C-reactive protein at pre-pubertal stage and increased chances of cardiovascular disease in later life.

Table 9. Comparison of dietary intake on the basis of C-reactive protein

Variables	Quantitative CRP (Mean±SD)		p-value
	Normal(N=41)	At risk(N=39)	
Calories (kcal/day)	1611.78 ± 183.39	2212.07 ± 169.95	0.000*
Carbohydrates(g/day)	167.86 ± 65.63	212.47 ± 84.09	0.010*
Fats (g/day)	69.36 ± 14.09	99.44 ± 11.21	0.000*
Protein (g/day)	52.93 ± 14.7	57.25 ± 12.83	0.168*
Fiber (g/day)	8.57 ± 1.60	7.47 ± 1.53	0.003*
Cholesterol (mg/day)	73.61 ± 30.38	123.55 ± 73.06	0.000*
Vitamin A (R.E)	55.11 ± 6.74	52.00 ± 6.39	0.037*

*= chi-square test, **= independent sample t-test

Association of quantitative C-reactive protein Level with anthropometric measurement

Effect of independent variables Weight, BMI, waist circumference and waist to hip ratio on

dependent variable C-reactive protein was shown in table 4.11. There was strong relation of Weight ($r=.425^{**}$, $p=0.000$), BMI ($r=.556^{**}$, $p=0.000$), waist circumference ($r=.439^{**}$, $p=0.000$) WHR ($r=.567^{**}$, $p= 0.003$) with Plasma C-reactive protein.

The result of the current observation shows resemblance with the work of Ford et al. (2005) who observed a positive relation of C-reactive protein and obesity in children. Increased level of CRP was noted in those subjects who were obese. The value of CRP increased with increasing BMI and WHR. National health and nutrition examination survey (1999-2002) also observed that adiposity was the best predictor of

increased level of C-reactive protein. Those Subjects who were overweight have high CRP and greater metabolic abnormalities. Obesity is one of determinant for high C-reactive protein level. Excess of macronutrient in adipose tissue encourage them to release inflammatory markers. Adipose tissues produce and release inflammatory and anti-inflammatory markers such as adiponectin, adipokine and cytokines such as interleukin 6. The high level of interleukin 6 stimulates the liver to produce and secrete C-reactive protein. Thus, increased in adiposity plasma C-reactive protein level also increased (Ellulu et al. 2017).

Table 10 Association of quantitative C - reactive protein Level with anthropometric measurement

Variables	r	p-value
Weight(kg)	0.425**	0.000
Height(inch)	-0.373**	0.001
BMI (kg/m ²)	0.556**	0.000
Waist circumference(cm)	0.439**	0.000
Hip circumference(cm)	0.282*	0.011
WHR (cm)	0.567**	0.003

r= correlation, *= significant at $p<0.05$, **= significant at $p<0.01$

Association of quantitative C-reactive protein with dietary nutrients

Table 11 shows the result of independent variables calories, carbohydrates, fibers, fats and vitamin A on dependent variable quantitative plasma C-reactive protein. The present study shows strong relation between C-reactive protein and caloric ($r=.639^{**}$, $p=0.00$) fats ($r=.561^{**}$, $p=0.00$) intake and negative relation with fiber ($r=-.237^*$, $p=0.034$) and vitamin A ($r=-.482$, $p=0.00$).

Results of the present study show resemblance with the observation of Mustafa et al. (2009) who reported that high consumption of grains,

vegetables and fruits in adults have been associated with low level of C-reactive protein. Fruits and vegetables are low energy dense food with high level of water and fiber. They are rich in antioxidant and lower the concentration of C-reactive protein reduced inflammation. Alvira et al. (2015) observed a positive significant relation of C-reactive protein with vegetables in children. Buyken et al. (2014) also reported an inverse association between fiber and plasma C- reactive protein in adults. Vegetable and fruits have high fiber content and therefore fiber have potential influence on C-reactive protein level in adults.

Table 11. Association of quantitative C-reactive protein with dietary nutrients

Variables	r	p-value
Calories (kcal/day)	0.639**	0.000
Carbohydrates(g/day)	0.061	0.591
Fats (g/day)	0.516**	0.000
Protein (g/day)	0.104	0.358
Fiber (g/day)	-0.237*	0.034
Cholesterol (mg/day)	0.223*	0.047
Vitamin A (R.E)	-0.233*	0.037

r= correlation, *= significant at p<0.05, **= significant at p<0.01

Association of quantitative C-reactive protein with physical activity

Table 12 shows the association of Quantitative C-reactive protein with physical activity. The effect of independent variables Exercise/other activity, Exercise frequency, exercise time, exercise type and sleeping hour in a day on dependent variable Quantitative C-reactive protein. Result of the present study shows no significant relation between C-reactive protein and physical activity (p=0.38, r=-.099), Exercise frequency (p=0.509, r=0.075), Exercise duration (p=0.070, r=0.203), physical activity level (p=0.135, r=0.169) and sleeping hour in a day (p=0.377, r=-.100).

Results of the present study show resemblance with the work of Joshoua Reid Veik (2013) who reported that physical activity have no effect on

plasma CRP in children having age 8-11 years old. Decrease in BMI percentile and percent body fat have no effect on C-reactive protein level. Further studies with larger sample size will be needed to investigate the relationship. Thomas et al. (2010) found that in adults there is evidence that increased physical activity decreases C-reactive protein level while physical activity has no impact on plasma C-reactive protein level in children of age 12-13years. Physical activity was consistently associated with lower C-reactive protein level in adults (6-35%). No significant relation was found between physical activity and C-reactive protein level in children.

Table 12. Association of quantitative C-reactive protein with physical activity

Variables	r	p-value
Exercise/other activity	-0.099	0.380
Exercise frequency	0.075	0.509
Exercise duration	0.203	0.070
Physical activity level	0.125	0.269
Sleeping hour in a day	-0.100	0.377

CONCLUSION

Our findings show that children’s health is shaped not only by biology but also by family education, socio-economic status, and daily food choices. Higher parental education was linked with lower inflammation, while limited

resources reduced access to nutritious foods. A notable proportion of children were overweight, and this excess weight was clearly tied to higher C-reactive protein levels, signalling early inflammation. Diet played a central role: more fats and cholesterol raised CRP, while fruits,

vegetables, fiber, and vitamins helped keep it down. Although nearly half of the children reported being physically active, activity alone did not appear to influence CRP in this group. Taken together, these results highlight the importance of empowering families with education, improving access to healthy foods, and tackling childhood obesity early. Supporting children in these areas may help reduce inflammation and protect them from future heart and metabolic problems.

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